

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Paper

Review on Isatin and it's Anticancer Scaffolds

Srajan Shetty*, Tejal Nikam, Vidya Kajale, Yogesh Zambare

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Krishnarao Bhegde Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 06 May 2026

Keywords:

Isatin, Indole-2,3-dione.
Heterocyclic compounds,
Isatin derivatives,
Anticancer agents,
Structure–activity
relationship

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20051853

ABSTRACT

Isatin (1H-indole-2,3-dione) is a privileged heterocyclic scaffold that has gained sustained attention in medicinal chemistry due to its wide range of biological activities and structural adaptability. Subtle modifications at the N-1, C-3, and C-5 positions of the isatin nucleus have led to the development of numerous derivatives with promising anticancer, antimicrobial, antiviral, and central nervous system activities. In recent years, hybridization of isatin with other pharmacophores and strategic structural optimization have resulted in compounds exhibiting enhanced potency, selectivity, and mechanistic diversity. This short review summarizes the chemical significance of isatin, highlights key synthetic approaches, and discusses representative biologically active isatin derivatives reported in recent literature. Emphasis is placed on structure–activity relationships and synthetic strategies that support the continued development of isatin-based molecules as valuable leads in drug discovery..

INTRODUCTION

Isatin (1H-indole-2,3-dione) is a biologically active heterocyclic compound that serves as a key structural motif in numerous natural and synthetic molecules. Since its first synthesis in the 19th century, isatin has gained considerable attention in medicinal chemistry due to its wide spectrum of pharmacological properties, including antimicrobial, antiviral, anticonvulsant, antioxidant, and anticancer activities.¹⁻⁵ Its unique

indole-dione framework provides reactive sites suitable for diverse chemical modifications, making it an important intermediate for drug design and synthesis.⁶⁻⁸

Recent studies have shown that isatin-based compounds exhibit a wide range of biological activities, with notable effects against different cancer cell lines such as breast, lung, colon, and leukemia models.¹¹⁻¹⁴ These derivatives act through several pathways including induction of

***Corresponding Author:** Srajan Shetty

Address: Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Krishnarao Bhegde Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research

Email ✉: srajans361@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

apoptosis, inhibition of cell proliferation, and interference with receptor tyrosine kinases like EGFR and VEGFR2.^{15,16} Apart from their anticancer role, many isatin analogues have also shown antioxidant, antimicrobial, anticonvulsant, and enzyme inhibitory activities, indicating their broad pharmacological potential.^{17,19}

Chemically, isatin is a versatile scaffold that can easily undergo condensation, cyclization, and Schiff base formation, leading to a variety of heterocyclic structures with improved biological activity. The metal-chelating ability of isatin-derived Schiff bases further enhances their

interaction with biomolecules, contributing to their diverse pharmacological profile.^{20,21}

In recent years, researchers have also emphasized more sustainable methods for synthesizing isatin derivatives, including the use of mild catalysts and natural extracts that minimize the use of toxic reagents. Such eco-friendly approaches reflect the current trend of combining medicinal chemistry with green chemistry principles to achieve safer and more efficient drug design.²²

Structure Activity Relationship (SAR) of Isatin

Figure 2. Structure Activity Relationship (SAR) of isatin

The isatin nucleus (1H-indole-2,3-dione) serves as a versatile pharmacophore exhibiting a wide spectrum of biological activities. Substitution at various positions on the indole ring (N-1, C-5, C-6, and C-7) and modifications at the C-2 and C-3 carbonyl groups significantly influence its pharmacological profile, particularly anticancer activity. The electronic nature, steric effects, and hydrogen-bonding potential of these substituents determine the interaction of isatin derivatives with biomolecular targets such as kinases, caspases, and topoisomerases.

1. Modifications at N-1 Position

- Substitution at the nitrogen atom (N-1) greatly affects lipophilicity and cellular permeability.
- Alkyl or aryl groups at this position enhance cytotoxic activity by improving membrane penetration and interaction with hydrophobic pockets of enzymes.
- N-benzyl and N-phenyl isatin derivatives have shown potent antiproliferative activity against breast and lung cancer cell lines.^{3,7,31}
- Example
 1. N-benzyl isatin

1-benzyl-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione

Figure 3. Structure of N-benzyl isatin

- 2. N-methylisatin

2-methyl-1*H*-isoindole-1,3(2*H*)-dione

Figure 4. Structure of N-methyl isatin

2. Substitution at C-5, C-6, and C-7 Positions

1. Electron-donating groups ($-\text{OCH}_3$, $-\text{OH}$) at C-5 or C-7 generally enhance activity due to improved hydrogen bonding and radical scavenging properties.
2. Electron-withdrawing groups ($-\text{Cl}$, $-\text{Br}$, $-\text{NO}_2$) at C-5 or C-6 increase cytotoxicity by promoting electrophilic character and enhancing binding with enzyme receptors.
3. 5-Fluoro and 5-Chloro isatin derivatives exhibit remarkable anticancer potential by inducing apoptosis in tumor cells.^{2,5,20,26}
4. Examples
 1. 5-Fluoroisatin

5-fluoro-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione

Figure 5. Structure of 5-Fluoro isatin

2. 7-Chloroisatin

7-chloro-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione

Figure 6. Structure of 7- Chloro isatin

3. 5-Nitroisatin

5-nitro-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione

Figure 7. Structure of 5-Nitro isatin

3. Modifications at the C-2 and C-3 Positions

- The C-3 carbonyl group is highly reactive and can form Schiff bases, hydrazones, or oximes, leading to enhanced cytotoxic and apoptosis-inducing properties.³
- C-3 hydrazone derivatives are particularly active due to their ability to chelate metal ions and generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cancer cells.^{14,34}
- The C-2 position can accommodate bulky or heterocyclic moieties, which may improve binding affinity toward cancer-related enzymes.
- Example

1. Isatin-3-hydrazone derivative

3-diazenyl-1*H*-indol-2-ol

Figure 8. Structure of Isatin-3-hydrazone

2. Isatin-thiosemicarbazones derivative

2-(2-oxo-1,2-dihydro-3*H*-indol-3-ylidene)hydrazine-1-carboth
Figure 9. Structure of Isatin thiosemicarbazone derivative

4. N-1 and C-3 Dual Substitution

- Simultaneous modification at N-1 and C-3 positions significantly improves selectivity and potency.
- N-1 aryl-C-3 hydrazone derivatives exhibit synergistic effects due to combined lipophilicity and enhanced receptor binding.^{7,10,13,28}
- These dual-substituted compounds have demonstrated broad anticancer efficacy against leukemia, colon, and ovarian cancer lines.^{3,14,28}
- Example

N-phenyl isatin-3-thiosemicarbazone derivative [7]

2-(2-oxo-1,2-dihydro-3*H*-indol-3-ylidene)hydrazine-1-carbothioamide

Figure 10. Structure of N-phenyl isatin-3-thiosemicarbazone derivative

5. Role of Heterocyclic Fusion

- Incorporation of heterocyclic rings (e.g., quinoline, pyridine, thiazole) into the isatin

scaffold expands conjugation and improves enzyme inhibition (like EGFR, Bcl-2, and caspase-3).^{12,13}

- Spiro-isatin derivatives and isatin-quinoline hybrids have been reported to display high selectivity toward tumor cells while minimizing normal cell toxicity.^{12,13,28}

- Example

Spiro[indole-3,4'-oxan]-2(1*H*)-one derivative¹

spiro[indole-3,4'-oxan]-2(1*H*)-one

Figure 11. Structure of spiro[indole-3,4'-oxan]-2(1*H*)-one derivative

Methods of synthesis of Isatin:

1. Sandmeyer method

The Sandmeyer reaction offers a well-established method for the synthesis of isatin from aniline derivatives. The process begins with the formation of an N-aryl oxime intermediate through the reaction of aniline with trichloroacetaldehyde (chloral hydrate) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride under acidic conditions. Subsequent acid-catalyzed cyclization of the oxime intermediate in the presence of sulfuric acid and water leads to the formation of isatin (1*H*-indole-2,3-dione). This reaction pathway efficiently constructs the isatin core and allows for various substitutions on the aromatic ring via the aniline precursor, making it a versatile approach for functionalized isatin synthesis.^{6,33}

Scheme 1. Sandmeyer Synthesis

2. Stolle's method

The Stolle synthesis is a widely recognized method for preparing N-substituted isatins from anilines. Initially, the aniline reacts with oxalyl chloride, leading to the formation of a chlorooxalylanilide intermediate with the elimination of hydrogen chloride. This intermediate subsequently undergoes

intramolecular cyclization in the presence of a Lewis acid catalyst, such as aluminium chloride (AlCl_3), yielding the corresponding isatin derivative. The reaction conditions are typically mild, and the method provides access to a variety of N-substituted isatins by simply varying the substituents on the starting aniline.^{6,25}

Scheme 2. Stolle's Synthesis method

3. Gassman method

The Gassman reaction offers a route starting from N-substituted anilines, which react with trichloro acetyl chloride followed by oxidation to produce

isatin derivatives. The advantage of this method is the ability to introduce substituents directly on the nitrogen atom, enabling the synthesis of various N-substituted isatins useful for biological screening.⁶

Scheme 3. Gassman Synthesis method

Most Potent Anticancer Isatin Derivatives :

1. Bis (indolin-2,3-dione) Hybrid

Figure 12. Structure of Compound 29

Althagafi et al. Synthesized a series of bis-(indoline-2,3-dione) via reactions of isatin with 1,3-dibromopropane with subsequent condensation reaction with hydrazine derivatives. The antiproliferative activity of the synthesized hybrids was assayed on MCF-7 cells and revealed some compounds exhibiting IC50s ranging from 0.0028 to 0.028 μm , with Compound 29 being the most potent, having an IC50 of 0.0028 μm on MCF-7 cancer cells.⁴²

Synthesis:

Scheme 4. Synthesis of Compound 29

2. N-Benzyl 5-Aryl Isatin

- Structure:

Figure 13. Structure of compound 51

Zhang et al. Synthesized a series of N-1 benzyl substituted 5-arylisatins and evaluated Their antiproliferative activities on human leukemia K562 and liver cancer hepg2 cells using An MTT

assay. The presence of N-benzyl and C-5 phenyl substituents along with an intact Carbonyl functionality at the C-3 position proved to be important for good antiproliferative Activities. Compound 51 proved to be the most potent among the series, exhibiting the Highest antiproliferative activity against K562 cells, with an IC₅₀ of 0.03 μm , while an IC₅₀ Of 0.05 μm was observed on hepg2 cells (Figure 8). The morphological results and flow Cytometry analysis revealed that the cell cycle arrest resulted in a time- and dose-dependent Manner. Additionally, the results of cell tube formation have shown the inhibition of the Angiogenesis of HUVEC cells by 51 via a dose-dependent inhibitory effect.¹¹

- Synthesis:

Scheme 5. Synthesis of compound 51

3, Indolin-2-one Thiadiazole Hybrid

Figure 14. Structure of compound 197

A panel of three cancer cell lines, namely colon (Caco-2), Hepatocellular (hepg2), and breast (MDA-MB-231) cancer cell Lines, was used to evaluate the potential anti proliferative effects Of

compound 197. It displayed IC₅₀ values of 2.0, 10, and 40 μM In comparison to DOX, which had IC₅₀ values of 3.46, 1.15, and 0.98 μM , respectively. It showed IC₅₀ values of 2.0, 10, and 40 μM , in contrast to DOX's IC₅₀ values of 3.46, 1.15, and 0.98 μM , respectively. The molecular dynamics and docking studies have revealed the presence of a stable complex that binds to the active areas of VEGFR2 with a high affinity of 197.¹²

• Synthesis

Scheme 6. Synthesis of compound 197

4. Isatin–thiazole-based hybrid

Figure 15. Structure of Compound 14

MTT-based screening assays against two cancer Cell lines MCF-7 (breast cancer) and HT-29 (colorectal Cancer) revealed some important structure activity trends. Compounds with phthalimide ring, thiadiazole moiety and 4-nitrophenyl group (attached to diazole ring)

displayed Higher activity than the compounds with alternative structure features (viz. Maleimide ring, oxadiazoles moiety and 4-hydroxyphenyl group). Compound C14 (2-(4-chloro-3-((5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)diazenyl)phenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-1H-isindole-1,3(2H)-dione) displayed Significant anticancer activity against both cell lines with IC₅₀ values of $0.09 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{M}$ (MCF-7) and $0.11 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{M}$ (HT-29).

Compound C16 displayed highest anticancer activity against MCF-7 cell line with IC₅₀ = $0.07 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{M}$. Compounds with thiadiazoles moiety (C5 to C16) showed higher cytotoxicity than their respective oxygen analogues.^{24,32}

Figure 16. Structure of compound 16

- Synthesis of compound 14 and 16 :

Scheme 7. Synthesis of compound 14 and 16

5. N-Substituted Isatin Thiosemicarbazone Metal Complexes

Figure 18. Structure of compound 40a

The group further extended the approach and synthesized a series of nickel(II) complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})_2]$ of N-substituted isatin thiosemicarbazones. In vitro cytotoxicity evaluation Revealed substantial activities on human breast (MCF7) and lung (A549) cancer cells, with The best outcomes being recorded for complexes 40a and 40b, exhibiting $\text{IC}_{50} < 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. Complexes 40a and 40b showed a stronger DNA binding affinity than the other Complexes, which could be attributed to the presence of benzyl and allyl groups.^{14,34}

Synthesis:

Scheme 8. Synthesis of compound 40a

6. Isatin- α , β -Unsaturated Ketone Hybrids

Figure 20. Structure of compound 5b

Compounds 5b and 5g were the most potent with IC₅₀ values $0.38 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{m}$ And $0.57 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{m}$, which are comparable with the positive control staurosporine. To Assess the safety of the synthesized compounds, we screened the cytotoxicity of the most Potent compound 5b on the normal peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC).

The Compound showed weak cytotoxicity on normal cells with an IC₅₀ value of $14.17 \mu\text{m}$, and Selectivity index (SI) of 37.2. These results demonstrated that the synthesized compounds Have selective cytotoxic activity against cancer cells, without affecting normal body cells. Therefore, the target compounds are promising anticancer lead compounds.

Figure 21. Structure of compound 5g
Synthesis:

Scheme 9. Synthesis of compound 5b and 5g.[39]

7. 5-Substituted Isatin-Capped Hydroxamic Acid Derivatives (HDAC Inhibitors)

Figure 22. Structure of compound 15

In a recent study, 5-substituted isatin capped hydroxamic Acid derivatives (15) have been reported as HDAC inhibitors and their anti-proliferative activity against cervical tumor cell lines Has been evaluated. SAR showed that halogenation of the parent Compound (15a) produced the most active compounds of the Series (15c, 15d, and 15e). Out of the halogenated compounds the 5-chloro-substituted derivative (15d) was found to be the Most potent, with $IC_{50} = 0.97 \pm 0.26 \mu m$.²⁰

8. Isatin Indole Hybrid

N-(1-benzyl-5-chloro-2-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-indol-3-yl)-1*H*-indole-2-carbohydrazide

Figure 23. Structure of compound 12c

Indoles constitute an important subunit for the discovery of new drug candidates. It is widely distributed in natural Products and bioactive molecules and is responsible for the faecal smell in human feces, scents of flowers, and the flowery Smell of perfumes [84–86]. The indole moiety is a versatile Molecule with several biological properties such as antifungal, antimicrobial, antiviral, and antitubercular properties.

The hybrid 12c showed potent antiproliferative activity with an IC_{50} value of $1.17 \mu m$ which was approximately sevenfold greater than Sunitinib, a well-known anticancer Medication. The SAR studies revealed that hybrids bearing N-benzyl moiety on isatin were more active with better antiproliferative activity.²³

9. Isatin Azole Hybrid

Figure 24. Structure of compound 2b

Azole, a privileged scaffold of choice when designing novel Therapeutic agents, is mainly found as core structure in several natural products and synthesized compounds that are used by pharmaceutical or agrochemical industries. Most azole compounds are used as antifungal drugs and some of its derivatives possess a variety of biological properties such as anticancer , antibacterial, and antitubercular properties. Several isatin-Azole hybrids have been synthesized and reported to possess diverse pharmacological properties. The hybrid 2b was identified as the most active analogue portraying

broad-spectrum Activity against breast, colon, and lung human cancer cell Lines with an average IC₅₀ value of 2.14 μ m. SAR studies Revealed that the 5-pyrazolyl moiety was crucial and played An important role in the enhanced activity of this compound.¹⁴

10. N-Benzyl and C-5 Phenyl-Substituted Isatin Derivatives

Figure 25. Structure of compound 2m

In conclusion, a series of novel N-1 benzyl and C-5 phenyl Substituted isatin derivatives were synthesized and tested for their In vitro antitumor activity against two strains of cancer cell lines (human leukemia K562 cells and liver cancer hepg2 cells). Among Them, compounds 2m exhibited excellent cancer inhibitory activity In

vitro against K562 cell lines (IC₅₀ $\frac{1}{4}$ 0.03 mm) and hepg2 cell lines (IC₅₀ $\frac{1}{4}$ 0.05 mm). SAR analysis showed that the carbonyl group of the isatin, N-benzyl and C-5 phenyl substituted pattern, the para-methoxyl group of the benzyl played a significant role in the anti-tumor activity. Both morphological results and flow cytometry analysis showed that compound 2m induce apoptosis and cause cell cycle arrest in a time-dependent and dose-dependent manner. Furthermore, wound healing and trans well experiments showed that compound 2m could inhibit the migration and repair ability of hepg2 cells. In Addition, the results of cell tube formation showed that the compound 2m could inhibit the angiogenesis of HUVEC cells and has a Dose-dependent inhibitory effect. The effects of indole derivative compound 2m on tumor cell growth, migration and angiogenesis were studied, which provide a Strong foundation for further study on the antitumor activity and mechanism of indole compounds.¹¹

- Synthesis:

Scheme 10. Synthesis of compound 2m

SUMMARY

This article focuses on understanding the chemistry, reactions and biological relevance of isatin. It begins with the basic methods used for the synthesis of isatin, including both classical approaches like the Sandmeyer and Stolle reactions, as well as modern techniques such as microwave-assisted and multicomponent

methods. The study then covers the major reactions of isatin, including oxidation, ring expansion, aldol and cross-aldol condensations, Friedel-Crafts reactions and various condensation pathways. These reactions highlight how easily the isatin structure can be modified. The article also reviews different isatin derivatives reported in literature and compares their biological activities. Among them, the α,β -unsaturated

hybrids, thiosemicarbazone metal complexes, hydroxamic-acid-based derivatives and N-benzyl/C-aryl substituted isatins appeared to be the most potent. Overall, the article provides a clear understanding of how synthetic modifications influence the pharmacological effects of isatin.

CONCLUSION

From the overall study, it is clear that isatin is a highly flexible and valuable scaffold in medicinal chemistry. The different reactions and synthetic methods discussed show how easily its structure can be changed to create new derivatives. The biologically active compounds reviewed also prove that certain substitutions on the isatin ring can significantly improve activity. In short, isatin remains an important starting point for designing new molecules, and the findings in this article help point toward the most promising directions for future work.

REFERENCES

1. Rajesh, S. M., Gowda, B., Srinivasa, S. M., Swaroop, T. R., Suresh, R. N., Shalini, V. G., Preetham, H. D., Shobith, R., & Rangappa, K. S. (2025). Synthesis of spiro[cyclopropane-isatin] derivatives and their therapeutic potential as anticancer agents against colorectal carcinoma. *Results in Chemistry*, 16, 102368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2025.102368>
2. Alkahtani, H. M., Alanazi, M. M., Aleanizy, F. S., Alqahtani, F. Y., Alhoshani, A., Alanazi, F. E., Almehizia, A. A., Abdalla, A. N., Alanazi, M. G., El-Azab, A. S., & Abdel-Aziz, A. A.-M. (2019). Synthesis, anticancer, apoptosis-inducing activities and EGFR and VEGFR2 assay mechanistic studies of 5,5-diphenylimidazolidine-2,4-dione derivatives: Molecular docking studies. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, 27(5), 682-693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsps.2019.04.003>
3. Kumar, S., Saha, S. T., Gu, L., Palma, G., Perumal, S., Singh-Pillay, A., Singh, P., Anand, A., Kaur, M., & Kumar, V. (2018). Structural optimization, synthesis, molecular docking, cytotoxicity evaluation, and cell-cycle analysis of N-acylhydrazones derived from isatin and indoline for antiproliferative activity on cancer cells. *ACS Omega*, 3(9), 12106-12113. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.8b01513>
4. D., J. M. ., P., J. K., N., N. S. ., M., . M. B., K., M. K., A., N. R., & P., P. C. (2025). Design, Characterization And Molecular Docking Of Isatin Derivative. *Journal of Neonatal Surgery*, 14(12S), 422-431. <https://doi.org/10.52783/jns.v14.3256>
5. Abdel-Aal, M. T., Sharshar, E. S., Elganzory, H. H., El-Bayaa, M. N., Awad, H. M., Ismail, A. E.-H. A. A., & El-Sayed, W. A. (2021). Synthesis and Anticancer Activity of New 1,3,4-Thiadiazolyl-1,2,4-Triazolyl and 1,3,4-Oxadiazolyl Hybrids, Their Thioglycosides, and Acyclic Analogs. *Russian Journal of Bioorganic Chemistry*, 47(6), 1324-1334. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S106816202106002>
6. Al-Khuzai, M. G. A., Fahad, M. M., & Al-Safi, A. J. (2022). A review on synthesis, reaction and biological importance of isatin derivatives. *Biomedicine and Chemical Sciences*, 1(3), 193-206. <https://doi.org/10.48112/bcs.v1i3.221>
7. Pandeya, S. N., Smitha, S., Jyoti, M., & Sridhar, S. K. (2005). Biological activities of isatin and its derivatives. *Acta pharmaceutica (Zagreb, Croatia)*, 55(1), 27-46.
8. Izmet'ev, A. N., Kravchenko, A. N., & Gazieva, G. A. (2022). Synthesis and antiproliferative activity characterization of new imidazothiazolotriazine oxindolylidene derivatives containing various substituents in

- the oxindole ring. *Chemistry of heterocyclic compounds*, 58(10), 531–538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10593-022-03125-3>
9. Khan, F., & Maalik, A. (2015). Advances in pharmacology of Isatin and its derivatives: A review. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 14, 1937. <https://doi.org/10.4314/tjpr.v14i10.28>
 10. Leylaty, M., Fatehpoor, R., Kashipazha, S., & Harati, S. (2021). Synthesis and anti-cancer activity evaluation of novel 1,3,4-oxadiazole substituted 5-arylidene/estarynidene-2-imino/thiazolidin-4-ones. *Biointerface Research in Applied Chemistry*, 12(1), 1861–1873. <https://doi.org/10.33263/BRIAC121.11611173>
 11. Kumar, D., Kumar, N. M., Noel, B., & Shah, K. (2012). A series of 2-arylamino-5-(indolyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles as potent cytotoxic agents. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 55, 432–438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2012.06.047>
 12. Kumar, N., Sharma, C. S., Singh, H. P., & Chauhan, L. S. (2017). Synthesis and in vitro evaluation of novel isatin-incorporated thiadiazole hybrids as potential anti-breast cancer agents. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 16(8), 1957–1963. <https://doi.org/10.4314/tjpr.v16i8.28>
 13. El-Sayed, H. A., El-Hashash, M. M., & Ahmed, A. E. (2018). Novel synthesis, ring transformation, and anticancer activity of 1,3-thiazine, pyrimidine, and triazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidine derivatives. *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Ethiopia*, 32(3), 513–520. <https://doi.org/10.4314/bcse.v32i3.10>
 14. Mushtaq, A., Asif, R., Humayun, W. A., & Naseer, M. M. (2024). Novel isatin–triazole based thiosemicarbazones as potential anticancer agents: Synthesis, DFT and molecular docking studies. *RSC Advances*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4ra01937g>
 15. Alshams, M. A., Nafie, M. S., Ashour, H. F., & Yassen, A. S. A. (2025). A comprehensive review and recent advances on isatin-based compounds as a versatile framework for anticancer therapeutics (2020–2025). *RSC Advances*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d5ra05002b>
 16. da Silva, J. F. M., Garden, S. J., & Pinto, A. C. (2001). The chemistry of isatins: A review from 1975 to 1999. *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*, 12(3), 327–353. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-50532001000300002>
 17. Kumar, K. S., Hanumappa, A., Hegde, M., Narasimhamurthy, K. H., Raghavan, S. C., & Rangappa, K. S. (2014). Synthesis and antiproliferative effect of novel 4-thiazolidinone-, pyridine- and piperazine-based conjugates on human leukemic cells. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 81, 341–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2014.05.009>
 18. Panga, S., Podila, N. K., Asres, K., & Ciddi, V. (2016). Synthesis and anticancer activity of new isatin-benzoic acid conjugates. *Ethiopian Pharmaceutical Journal*, 31(2), 75–92. <https://doi.org/10.4314/epj.v31i2>
 19. Roman, O., & Lesyk, R. (2007). Synthesis and anticancer activity in vitro of some 2-thioxo-4-thiazolidone derivatives. *Farmacia*, 15, 640–648.
 20. Ferraz de Paiva, R. E., Vieira, E. G., Rodrigues da Silva, D., Wegermann, C. A., & Costa Ferreira, A. M. (2021). Anticancer compounds based on isatin-derivatives: Strategies to ameliorate selectivity and efficiency. *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences*, 7, 627272. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmolb.2020.627272>

21. Vineethchandy, V., Visagaperumal, V., Rabiubala, A., & Sangeetha, K. S. (n.d.). A review on isatin derivatives with anti-cancer activity. Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, T. John College of Pharmacy, Bangalore, India. Unpublished manuscript.
22. Hamzehloueian, M., Sarrafi, Y., Darroudi, M., Azimzadeh Arani, M., Nezamdoost Darestani, R., Safari, F., & Foroumadi, A. (2023). Synthesis, antibacterial and anticancer activities evaluation of new 4-thiazolidinone-indolin-2-one analogs. *Biointerface Research in Applied Chemistry*, 12(6), 8104-8115. <https://doi.org/10.33263/BRIAC126.80948104>
23. Potkin, V., Kletskov, A., Petkevich, S., Pashkevich, S., Kazbanov, V. V., Denisov, A., & Kulchitsky, V. (2015). Synthesis of water soluble isoxazol-3-yl(isothiazol-3-yl) carboxamides and ureas containing amino acid residues – potential anticancer agents. *Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry*, 1, 11–19.
24. Andrade, I. M. G., Lima Filho, E. de O., Valadão, C. F., Forezi, L. da S. M., & Silva, F. de C. da. (2025). Recent advances in isatin–thiazole hybrids: Synthesis, structural design, and biological application. *Chemistry & Biodiversity*, e01989. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbdv.202501989>
25. Mathur, G., & Nain, S. (2014). Recent advancement in synthesis of isatin as anticonvulsant agents: A review. *Medicinal Chemistry*, 4(4), 417-427. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2161-0444.1000173>
26. Karati, D. (2024). An insight into isatin and its hybrid scaffolds as anti-cancer agents: An explicative review. *Discover Chemistry*, 1, 66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44371-024-00073-z>
27. SEARCH FOR BIOLOGICAL ACTIVE ISATINS: A SHORT REVIEW. (2010). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research*, 2(4), 229-235. <https://doi.org/10.25004/IJPSDR.2010.020402>
28. El-Azab, A. S., Al-Dhfyhan, A., Abdel-Aziz, A. A.-M., Abou-Zeid, L. A., Alkahtani, H. M., Al-Obaid, A. M., & Al-Gendy, M. A. (2017). Synthesis, anticancer and apoptosis-inducing activities of quinazoline–isatin conjugates: Epidermal growth factor receptor-tyrosine kinase assay and molecular docking studies. *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry*, 32(1), 935-944. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14756366.2017.1344981>
29. Altamimi, M., Syed, S. A., Tuzun, B., Alhazani, M. R., Alnemer, O., & Bari, A. (2024). Synthesis, biological evaluation, and molecular docking of isatin hybrids as anti-cancer and anti-microbial agents. *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry*, 39(1), 2288548. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14756366.2023.2288548>
30. Sancak, K., Ünver, Y., & Er, M. (2007). Synthesis of 2-acylamino, 2-arylamino and ethoxycarbonyl imino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles as antitumor agents. *Turkish Journal of Chemistry*, 31(2), Article 2. <https://journals.tubitak.gov.tr/chem/vol31/iss2/2>
31. Rani, S. S., Gurunath, S., Sriram, R., & Sarangapani, M. (n.d.). Synthesis, characterization and in-vitro cytotoxic activity of N-alkyl derivatives of isatin. *Pharmacie Globale: International Journal of Comprehensive Pharmacy*. Retrieved from <http://www.pharmacie-globale.info/>
32. Bhatt, P., Kumar, M., & Jha, A. (2018). Synthesis, docking and anticancer activity of azo-linked hybrids of 1,3,4-thia-/oxadiazoles with cyclic imides. *Molecular Diversity*, 22,

- 827–840. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11030-018-9832-5>
33. Aziz, T., Ullah, A., Ullah, R., Haq, F., Iqbal, M., et al. (2020). Synthesis of isatin and its derivatives and their applications in biological system. *Biomedical Journal of Scientific & Technical Research*, 30(4). <https://doi.org/10.26717/BJSTR.2020.30.004991>
 34. Sabet, R. (2017). Synthesis of Some Novel Semicarbazone and Thiosemicarbazone Derivatives of Isatin as Possible Biologically Active Agents. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*. <https://doi.org/10.9734/JPRI/2017/35243>
 35. Elhady, H. (2015). Convenient synthesis of 1,3-disubstituted-2-thioxo-imidazolidin-4-ones as potential anti-tumor agents. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 3(1), 340–351.
 36. Iqbal, K., Bano, R., Hafeez, F., Khan, Z. A., Suleman, M., Mubarra, M., Zafar, A., & Abbas, S. (2024). Design, synthesis, characterization, and biological studies of isatin derivatives. *Journal of Xi'an Shiyou University, Natural Science Edition*, 20(2), 787-792.
 37. Vasilevskii, S. V., Nelyubina, Y. V., Kolotyrykina, N. G., Belyakov, P. A., Kulikova, L. B., & Kravchenko, A. N. (2010). Reaction of 1,3-dimethyl-3a,9a-diphenyl-3,3a,9,9a-tetrahydroimidazo-[4,5-e]-1,3-thiazolo[3,2-b]-1,2,4-triazine-2,7(1H,6H)-dione with isatins. *Mendeleev Communications*, 20(5), 288-290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mencom.2010.09.017>
 38. Ram, V. J., Sethi, A., Nath, M., & Pratap, R. (2019). Five-Membered Heterocycles. In V. J. Ram, A. Sethi, M. Nath, & R. Pratap (Eds.), *The Chemistry of Heterocycles* (pp. 149–478). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-101033-4.00005-X>
 39. Hamdy AK, Sakamoto T, Toma T, Sakamoto M, Abourehab MAS, Otsuka M, Fujita M, Tateishi H, Radwan MO. New insights into the structural requirements of isatin-derived pro-apoptotic agents against acute myeloid leukemia. *Pharmaceuticals*. 2022;15(12):1579. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph15121579>
 40. Chowdhary S, Shalini, Arora A, Kumar V. A mini review on isatin, an anticancer scaffold with potential activities against neglected tropical diseases (NTDs). *Pharmaceuticals*. 2022;15(5):536. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph15050536>
 41. *Med. Chem. Commun.*, 2019, 10, 351 [rsc.li/medchemcomm DOI:10.1039/c8md00585k](https://doi.org/10.1039/c8md00585k)
 42. Althagafi, I. I., Abouzied, A. S., Farghaly, T. A., Al-Qurashi, N. T., Alfaifi, M. Y., Shaaban, M. R., and Abdel Aziz, M. R. (2019) Novel Nano-sized bis-indoline Derivatives as Antitumor Agents. *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 56: 391–399. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jhet.3410>
 43. Shu, V.A., Eni, D.B. & Ntie-Kang, F. A survey of isatin hybrids and their biological properties. *Mol Divers* 29, 1737–1760 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11030-024-10883-z>
 44. Izmet'ev, A.N., Kravchenko, A.N. & Gazieva, G.A. Synthesis and antiproliferative activity characterization of new imidazothiazolotriazine oxindolydene derivatives containing various substituents in the oxindole ring. *Chem Heterocycl Comp* 58, 531–538 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10593-022-03125-3>

HOW TO CITE: Srajan Shetty, Tejal Nikam, Vidya Kajale, Yogesh Zambare, Review on Isatin and it's Anticancer Scaffolds, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 1096-1110, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20051853>

